

ID	Name	Description	Data and assumptions	Impact
1	Translating Crowdin first, then Amara content	The team firstly translates the Crowdin and then moves to the Amara content. It signifies that in order for the Amara team to start the translation they always need the Crowdin team to finish. However, the translations on these platforms are not connected.	<p>Data: In order to finish translating the Crowdin content, the stakeholders need to spend 14137.65 minutes, and this is 20199.8 minutes for the Amara content.</p> <p>There are 5 stakeholders who work in the Amara translation team.</p> <p>Assumptions: Proofreaders will be able to proofread the same content on Amara and Crowdin parallelly.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: In total, it takes 34337.45 minutes to finish both the Crowdin and Amara translations. By doing so, the team wastes additional 14137.65 minutes.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: It frustrates the Amara team to wait for the Crowdin team always.</p> <p>Unnecessary waiting time.</p>
2	The name of the task is not the same	The name of the tasks can be different because the coordinator uses the name from the translation dashboard, and it is not the same as the Crowdin (localization portal).	<p>Data: This case only happens with one coordinator.</p> <p>It takes the Crowdin translator to find the task for around 15 minutes.</p> <p>Assumption: This case happens within 2% frequency of all cases.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: There is a 15 minutes delay before starting the translation.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Demotivated translators.</p>
3	Misusing the localization platforms	In general, both in Crowdin and Amara, translators are not able to use the features effectively or they misuse some features such as	<p>Data: The team needs 2 days and 8 hours to solve the problems caused by the translators, on average.</p> <p>Assumption: This happens at 0.3%</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: When this kind of problem emerges, then it takes 3360 minutes to solve.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Misusing these features directly demotivates the</p>

		“Smart translations”.	frequency of all times.	work of team leader, project manager, proofreaders.
4	The quality of the translations is not satisfactory by the team.	Translators and proofreaders on Amara and Crowdin are different people, and terminologies might be translated differently on these two various platforms.	<p>Data: The quality control team spends 5783.2 minutes in general to control the quality, and its around 1227 minutes is due to the time spent on correcting the mistakes which appeared due to this issue.</p> <p>There are around 200 monthly users of the platform.</p> <p>Assumption: The team loses 20% of all monthly users due to the low quality content.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: 1227 minutes wasted to fix the mistakes.</p> <p>$200 * 0.2 = 40$ lost students each month.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Extra work for the quality control team.</p> <p>Unsatisfied users.</p>
5	Finding videos on Amara is hard	Some videos are not found on the Amara because either their names or IDs are different, or they have not been uploaded to the Amara at all.	<p>Data: The Amara translator spends 2767.8 minutes to find the videos on Amara.</p> <p>Assumption: The Amara translator postpones the translation when this problem emerges.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: In order to find the the videos, the mAara translator wastes 2767.8 minutes</p> <p>Due to translators` postpone, the team wastes 2 days. Due to translators` postpone, the team wastes 2 days.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Unhappy translators.</p>
6	Crowdin`s proposed translations damage the quality of translation	Crowdin proposes the translations, and sometimes they are not appropriate translations. When the user translates	<p>Data: There are around 200 monthly users of the platform.</p> <p>The proofreader needs to spend 10275 minutes.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: $200 * 0.2 = 40$ lost students each month.</p> <p>The Crowdin proofreaders wastes $[10080 + (30\% - 20\%) * 650] = 30$</p>

		it, then it directly spoils the quality of localization.	<p>Assumption: The team loses 20% of all monthly users due to the low quality content.</p> <p>Without this problem, the error rate within the proofreading process would decrease from 30% to 20% for text-format proofreading.</p>	<p>minutes.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Churned users.</p> <p>Bad learning experience of learners.</p>
7	Software key needs to be asked every time.	Software key is given only when the video editor faces the problem.	<p>Data: The video editor waits for 290.2 minutes to get the software key.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: 290.2 minutes were wasted to get the software key.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Demotivated video editor.</p>
8	Unmapped videos cannot be determined.	While mapping the videos, language advocate misses some unmapped videos, and finding them is a time-consuming process.	<p>Data: The Language Advocate spends 276.6 to find the unmapped videos.</p> <p>Assumption: The possibility of missing the unmapped video can be with 40% less frequency.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: The language advocate wastes</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Frustrated language advocate</p>
9	Proofreading takes longer.	The least number of team members is proofreaders, and it decreases the speed of the localization process.	<p>Data: There are 2 proofreaders in the team.</p> <p>Assumption: There are 4 translators who possess enough capabilities to be a proofreader.</p> <p>Each newly-uploaded content leads 2 new users per day.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: Losing the possibility of producing 4 more content.</p> <p>Losing to get 6 new users per day rather than to have 2 new users per day.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Demotivated stakeholders.</p>

10	Quality control team spends additional time checking the same document three times.	Language advocate, project manager, and content specialist check and ask to edit the video from the video editor separately. It signifies that the same document is checked three times, and the video editor needs to implement these changes three times.	<p>Data: The general quality control team spends 5783.8 minutes.</p> <p>Assumption: Project manager, the content specialist, and the language advocate are able to collaborate on the same document, and it makes the quality control cycle time to continue for 1185.6 minutes.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: Wasting 3598.2 (5738.8-1185.6) minutes every time.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Frustrated video editor. Unnecessary extra work.</p>
11	Notifying problems is a time-consuming process.	When any problems occur, then the translators need to communicate with coordinators, then they need to notify the team leader. After it, the team leader notifies the project manager.	<p>Data: Hiring new volunteers requires 2 weeks.</p> <p>Assumption: 5 volunteers leave the team due to this issue, and at least 4 of them can be kept in the team.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: Losing 5 volunteers monthly. Waiting for the new stakeholders for 2 weeks additionally.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Unhappy translators</p>
12	Texts on video screens are not translated properly.	Texts on the screen of the video, and video`s script are translated by different people, and it decreases the quality of the translation.	<p>Data: There are around 1000 views for the videos on YouTube.</p> <p>Assumption: 5% of YouTube viewers do not watch the video until the end due to this issue.</p>	<p>Quantitative impact: $1000 * 0.05 = 50$ churned viewers on YouTube.</p> <p>Qualitative impact: Unnecessary extra work.</p>

Table 1. Issue register analysis of the localization process of the Khan Academy content into Azerbaijani language